
Hypertree Decompositions for Query Optimization in Postgres

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

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Hypertree Decompositions for Query Optimization in Postgres - Detailed DMP

1. Data summary

State the purpose of the data collection/generation

The data is collected for the purpose of benchmarking the new, optimized queries and measure the effectiveness of the technique against the default postgres optimizer.

Explain the relation to the objectives of the project

The output consists of several directories of files (detailed data) and a summary CSV file with a shorter record for each directory. In each directory, which corresponds to a run of a query over a database on a database size, 6 files are deposited: a PostgreSQL function of the final generated query, the hypergraph in a custom format, a PDF of the rendered hypergraph, the original SQL query, detailed JSON output of the benchmark result, the join tree in a custom format.

Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected

A summary file: summary.csv

A directory structure:

{dbName}

- {queryname}-{algorithm}-{dbSize}-{runNr}
- query.sql (the original query in standard SQL)
- hypergraph.dtl (the hypergraph structure of the query in a simple text-based format)
- hypergraph.pdf (a graphic representation of the hypergraph)
- generated.sql (the PL/pgSQL function generated by the optimizer)
- result.json (the BenchmarkResult class serialized to JSON, containing detailed information)
- result.txt (unstructured debugging output)

The formats were chosen mainly due to pragmatic reasons. summary.csv provides a quick overview and most important information. JSON was chosen for detailed output because it is easy to interpret and Java objects can be serialized to it with low effort.

Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)

Existing data is not re-used except arguably the TPC-H benchmark, however there only the generator is reused. The configuration for data generation could however also be seen as data.

Specify the origin of the data

The origin of the data is generally the project itself, except, as seen from the last point, the TPC-H benchmark data.

State the expected size of the data (if known)

The expected size of the data generated in one run is between 1 and 10 MB. However, generated PDFs make up a large part of the size so it could be cut down significantly.

Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

Data will be useful for researchers investigating query optimization or extending the work of the thesis.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata [FAIR data]

Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision)

Discoverability of the data is not as important for the project as opposed to experiments generating new non-derived data, since the utility of the data itself produced in this experiment is low and its main use is to draw conclusions in the thesis itself. It may however be used to benchmark further novel attempts to improve query optimization.

Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?

Output data is identifiable via the timestamp and the detailed output of the configuration as JSON.

Outline naming conventions used

Due to automation of the whole process, naming is automatically kept consistent. Otherwise, no naming standards apply or are needed.

Outline the approach towards search keyword

Keyword search is not considered since the data produced can only be used together with the code of the thesis. The thesis itself will however be published at least in the TU library where it will be findable via keywords and it refers to the data.

Outline the approach for clear versioning

The versioning approach used is to create a new database configuration when something is changed and keep the old versions. Each database is identified by a unique name.

Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how

There are no applicable metadata standards. All configuration and part of the output is considered metadata for this experiment

2.2 Making data openly accessible [FAIR data]

Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so

All code and configuration is made openly available. All output data that is of relevance for the final thesis will also be openly available.

Specify how the data will be made available

Code is already available on the github repository: <https://github.com/arselzer/HTQueryOptimizer>.
Data will also be published there due to practical reasons in the form of GitHub releases.

Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

It is needed to install the dependencies specified in the README (maven, java, python, postgresql) to run the experiment. The data itself can be accessed over HTTP or via the git repository.

Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

Everything is on GitHub: <https://github.com/arselzer/HTQueryOptimizer>

Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions

N/A since there will be no restrictions.

2.3 Making data interoperable [FAIR data]

Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.

As the data is very domain-specific and experiment-specific, interoperability is low.

However, standard file formats for which many parsers exist (JSON, CSV) are used, making it possible to import data in many languages, etc. The tools are also cross-platform and open source and will therefore not only work on Linux and my development computers but everywhere if needed.

Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No, this is not applicable to the project since it is not inter-disciplinar.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses) [FAIR data]

Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible

The data will be licensed like the existing code - under the MIT license. This is identical to the CC0 license except for one restriction: it cannot be re-licensed arbitrarily, but it is a popular standard for open source software and well known.

Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed

All data used in the thesis will be made available before completing the thesis, as soon as useful, without any embargoes.

Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why

The data is usable, however it is, as explained before, of very limited use except for highly related experiments.

Describe data quality assurance processes

Configuration will be simplified as much as sensibly possible and unneeded data is reduced. The number of runs is configurable since the benchmarking is performed on computer hardware where performance can randomly vary. Then outliers can be detected if possible.

Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

There is no limit on the time the data will remain re-usable. As long as GitHub keeps their service up, the data is still accessible.

3. Allocation of resources

Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs

Complete dockerization: 3h, Testing reproducibility: 4h. Total: 7h. The costs are however 0 since the project is unpaid.

Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project

The writer of the thesis is responsible for all aspects of data management, since all others that are involved have supporting roles but do not contribute code to the core projects.

Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation

There are no costs associated with long term preservation since the data is public under a permissive license and can therefore be hosted for free.

4. Data security

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

Secure storage is not required since no sensitive data is stored. Therefore also no anonymization is needed. Data recovery is given since all work is done in a GitHub repository and GitHub is considered reliable enough for long-term storage.

5. Ethical aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

There are no ethical or legal issues associated with the project. No personal information is used and all dependencies are open-source.

6. Other

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

None